
WHITE PAPER

Towards an Open ESM Framework for Climate Intelligence in Europe

A case for coordinated open infrastructure to strengthen European climate modelling capacity, scientific autonomy, and policy relevance

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On behalf of the Open ESM Framework community (40 signatories across 10 countries)

Addressed to European research funders, climate modelling institutions, and science policymakers

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The Challenge

Europe faces urgent demands for reliable climate information not met by existing collective infrastructure:

- **Adaptation planning** requires regional-to-local projections, with robust uncertainty assessment
- **Industrial decarbonisation** needs integrated assessment linking physical climate and impacts to economic/energy system/land management models
- **Security and resilience planning** demands rapid-response scenario capabilities
- **Policy support** requires transparent, reproducible, defensible climate projections
- **Renewable energy** is increasingly dependent on accurate climate information
- **Cost of inaction** assessments rely on accurate climate projections

The upcoming [Horizon Europe framework \(2028-2034\)](#) calls for research that addresses societal challenges including climate change, with emphasis on competitiveness, strategic autonomy, and breakthrough technologies with "[Clean Transition and Industrial Decarbonisation](#)" as a key cluster.

However, current distributed European climate modelling infrastructure is not well positioned to respond to these demands at scale.

The Gap

Current European climate modelling capabilities are excellent scientifically but remain fragmented:

- Institutional models ([IPSL-CM](#), [CNRM-ESM](#), [UKESM](#)) respect mostly national priorities with dedicated codebases — appropriate for their missions, but not designed for broad community access or rapid adaptation to new applications
- AI integration is being pursued within [individual institutions](#) and [projects](#) but not systematically across European ESM development communities
- Limited interoperability between modelling centres [impedes multi-model approaches](#) and uncertainty quantification
- Coupling to impact/economic/energy models is ad hoc and generally unidirectional, [hindering integrated assessment for policy](#)
- Training pipelines are fragmented; no unified pathway for new researchers to contribute or develop, with closed code and HPC systems providing barriers to inclusivity

None of the existing European climate modelling systems fully satisfies the criteria for an open, accessible, problem-oriented platform that can serve the breadth of climate intelligence needs. Meeting these needs requires infrastructure that is responsive to European priorities, accessible to European researchers, and robust to external funding disruptions. The question is not whether to build new capacity, but how to coordinate and develop what already exists.

Fundamental Science as Strategic Infrastructure

Applications require understanding. Climate services, adaptation planning, and decarbonisation pathways are critically dependent on solid underlying science. AI-enhancements [provide opportunities](#), but must be developed in tandem with physics-based models and process-level knowledge to provide confidence in their application to future projections.

This creates a strategic concern: if fundamental climate science capacity erodes, the applications built on it will be unreliable, and Europe will become dependent on other actors, possibly driven by different interests, for state-of-art projection capabilities

Two simultaneous pressures make this risk acute:

1. **US capacity under threat:** The US National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR; <https://ncar.ucar.edu/>) has historically provided significant global capacity for fundamental, curiosity-driven climate modelling research. The [US administration plans to dismantle the center](#) reduces the worldwide base of process-level understanding that supports application-based research worldwide.
2. **Evolving EU funding orientation:** The [shift toward competitiveness-focused, application-driven research funding](#) is understandable in the current political climate, but risks underinvesting in the fundamental science that applications require. Short-term decision-support tools cannot substitute for long-term investment (e.g. in understanding cloud feedbacks, carbon cycle dynamics, or ocean circulation).

This is not an argument against application-based science, but one for recognising that applications critically depend on fundamental science quality.

A strategic approach to providing European climate intelligence

We propose that a dedicated effort is required to achieve **three goals**:

- Maintain capacity for **process-level research** across centres, not just service delivery
- Ensure that **AI integration** augments rather than substitutes for physical understanding
- Recognise that **scientific autonomy** (the ability to independently assess climate risks without dependence on any single external partner) is a component of European strategic autonomy and resilience

The opportunity outlined in this white paper addresses both needs: building application-ready infrastructure while strengthening the fundamental science base that makes applications trustworthy.

The Opportunity

We propose developing an **open infrastructure for climate intelligence** that:

1. **Amplifies the impact of funding** — strengthening shared infrastructure creates efficiencies, improving the effectiveness of strategic funding
2. **Serves diverse applications** from fundamental science, to adaptation planning, to industrial decarbonisation
3. **Fosters collaboration on AI**, with data-driven model components, ML-assisted analysis, AI-supported coding and documentation
4. Couples Earth system models to **decision-relevant models** such as economic models, land & energy models, sectoral impact models
5. **Lowers barriers** to entry and is accessible to researchers across Europe, not just major modelling centres
6. Enables **rapid response** by being flexible enough to address emerging policy questions on relevant timescales

In short, building **common infrastructure** (shared tools, workflows, training, and coordination) would make European climate research more productive, more responsive, and more impactful.

Building on the Open ESM Framework

To bootstrap this effort, we propose building and expanding on what we call the **Open ESM Framework**: open-source infrastructure (scripting, testing, coupling, data tools, and shared components) that already underpins significant European climate research.¹

Models built on the Open ESM Framework:

- [NorESM](#) (Norway, Sweden) — Arctic climate, aerosol-climate interactions, carbon cycle
- [CMCC-ESM](#) (Italy) — Mediterranean climate, ocean biogeochemistry, seasonal and decadal predictions
- [CESM](#) (International) — used and co-developed by multiple centres within Europe, highly adaptable with strong international training and usage community

Each of these models are [notable exemplifications](#) of free/libre open source software ([FLOSS](#)) with development climate models where code, input data and full model development cycles are fully transparent and open to the wider climate community.

Components developed and used across European institutions:

- [CLM\(-FATES\)](#) (Community Land Model) — extensively used across Europe (see Appendix A) for land-atmosphere interactions, agriculture, hydrology. And novel demographic components FATES to plant mortality and competition.
- [CAM\(-Chem\)](#) — atmospheric dynamics and gas-phase chemistry and aerosols
- [WACCM\(-X\)](#) - whole atmosphere model used to simulate stratospheric ozone/dynamics and space weather
- [CICE](#) — sea ice dynamics
- [CISM](#) — ice sheet dynamics
- [MOSART](#), [RTM](#) — river models
- [WW3](#) — wave model

¹This encompasses multiple technical elements including CIME (scripting/testing), CMEPS (coupling), CDEPS (data models), and shared model components — collectively forming an open, community-governed framework for Earth System Modelling.

Shared infrastructure benefiting all users:

- **Coupling tools** ([CMEPS - Community Mediator for Earth Prediction Systems](#)) and build systems enabling flexible model configurations
- **Data model functionality** ([CDEPS - Community Data Models for Earth Prediction Systems](#)) for standardised forcing and boundary conditions as well as flexibly enabling customization of component feedbacks as part of model development
- **Regional [grid refinement](#)** - allowing efficient use of computational resources to increase horizontal resolution in regions of particular interest for climate processes or impacts
- Case control and **scripting infrastructure** ([CIME - Community Infrastructure for modelling the Earth](#))
- **[Regression and unit testing frameworks](#)** enabling [reproducibility](#) and robustness of code across diverse computational platforms
- **[Ensemble generation toolkits](#)** - enabling the production and analysis of large parameter perturbation and initial condition ensembles to improve model calibration workflows
- **[Machine learning components](#)** - emulator tools to act as fast proxies for model components, allowing model acceleration and flexible data assimilation
- **[Model post-processing evaluation tools](#)** - allowing **rapid assessment of model response** and automatic generation of commonly requested climate metrics
- Training materials, [tutorials](#), and [documentation](#)

The Open ESM Framework is already as of today a **community-governed infrastructure without borders**. Development contributions come from multiple continents and the governance is assured through open scientific working groups. This makes it the natural foundation for coordination in global climate modelling.

Current [threats to US funding for CESM support](#) present a reminder that there is an opportunity to strengthen and steer this capacity through broader international engagement. Coordination through the Open ESM Framework provides direct European opportunities for further useful development:

- Systematic AI integration across components
- Standardised coupling to economic/impact models
- European-hosted training and community infrastructure
- Coordination mechanism for distributed development across Europe and beyond

The current threat to NCAR funding creates uncertainty for one major node in this ecosystem. This is a risk for climate modelling; but also an **opportunity to build a more distributed, resilient infrastructure** where European institutions play a more integrative role. The goal is to ensure that the framework thrives regardless of funding fluctuations in any one country.

Relationship to Existing European Efforts

This proposal of building and expanding an open ESM framework complements rather than competes with existing European modelling:

- Institutional models will continue serving their missions; this framework will provide a library of open components which can be drawn on in the centres associated to the institutional models
- Open ESM Framework models (NorESM, CMCC-ESM) will benefit from strengthened shared infrastructure
- Component users (CLM, CAM, CICE, CISM, MOSART, RTM, WW3 across multiple institutions, plus users of CESM) gain coordination and support
- ENES-RI, the European Network for Earth System Modelling research infrastructure, could naturally integrate with or inform this work

The structural diversity of European climate modelling is of great scientific value. We are not proposing consolidation. We are proposing that the subset of European research already using community modelling tools coordinate to facilitate efficiency and communication, making those tools more powerful while contributing most effectively to wider research community infrastructure.

Roadmap

Phase	Focus	Actions
Phase 1: Foundation (2026)	Community building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Open ESM workshop to map capabilities and identify priorities • Establish lightweight coordination mechanism (mailing list, common repositories, online seminars)
	Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data mirroring for key input datasets (resilience) Targeted collaborations: evaluation tools, lossy compression, infrastructure • Travel support for cross-Atlantic workshop participation
	Strategic planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scope AI integration opportunities across components Identify priority coupling interfaces with impact models (work with ISIMIP) • Improve ESM interfaces with IAMs and energy system models (with IAMC and Scenario Compass Initiative) • Develop funding strategy for Phase 2
Phase 2: Development (2027–2028)	Infrastructure development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European-hosted training programme • AI-enhanced component development • Standardised interfaces for impact model coupling • Distributed code development and testing infrastructure
	Funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New Horizon Europe proposals (2028–2034 programme) • COST Action for networking/coordination • National funding council engagement • Philanthropic sources for specific innovations
Phase 3: Integration (2029+)	Operational capability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrated climate intelligence platform serving diverse European users • AI-assisted workflows from model configuration through analysis • Routine coupling to policy-relevant economic/impact models • Sustainable governance and funding model

What We're Asking For

Audience	Asks
European funders (EC, national councils)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Recognition of open climate modelling infrastructure as strategic infrastructure for European competitiveness and climate resilience• Support for coordination activities in near term• Inclusion of community modelling infrastructure in Horizon Europe 2028–2034 priorities
European institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Engagement from groups already using Open ESM Framework tools• Willingness to coordinate across centres• Contributions to shared infrastructure development
NCAR/UCAR	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Continued partnership and openness to distributed development• Clarity on where European contributions add most value• Collaboration on AI integration strategy

Why Now

Three factors create a window of opportunity:

1. **Horizon Europe 2028-2034** is in the development phase; making large-scale priorities clear is critical
2. **AI transformation** is happening regardless, in climate as in all fields; the question is whether European climate modelling leads or follows
3. **International coordination:** the community of European Open ESM Framework users is mobilised and ready to build robust community research capacity

The goal is not to respond to a crisis. The goal is to build infrastructure that will be robust and valuable, allowing researchers to coordinate internationally and provide the best possible information during a challenging era.

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Appendix A. Survey of Open ESM Framework Usage in Europe

Full model usage (CESM, NorESM, CMCC-ESM) and individual components (CLM, POP, CICE, CAM, etc.)

Institution	Country	Model/Component	Active Projects	Contact(s)
CICERO	Norway	NorESM2, CESM2, CLM(FATES)	FUTURA NorESM4CMIP7 (Norw.RC) INES2 (Norw.RC) NextGenCarbon NorSink (Norw.RC) BorealBlaze, TargetBC, ARIDITY ICOS RealESM	benjamin.sanderson@cicero.oslo.no rosie.fisher@cicero.oslo.no
ETH	Switzerland	CLM, CESM runs with nudged circulation, CESM scenario runs, CESM ensemble boosting, variable resolution CAM, CAM-Chem simulations	FUTURA (pending) CLIMATEXSCALE (pending) QUEST (pending)	sonia.seneviratne@ethz.ch , reto.knutti@env.ethz.ch , robert.jnglinwills@env.ethz.ch , erich.fischer@env.ethz.ch colette.heald@env.ethz.ch
Forschungszentrum	Germany	eCLM, fork of CLM5, with own	Several, e.g. SFB DETECT, ESA Crops4EU,	h.hendricks-franssen@fz-juelich.de

Institution	Country	Model/Component	Active Projects	Contact(s)
Julich GmbH		developments. Part of terrestrial ESM TSMP	BMBF MW3, BMBF ITMS and others	
VUB	Belgium	CESM & CLM	SPARCCL FUTURA TIIMPACTS CropWaves	wim.thiery@vub.be
University of Sheffield	UK	CESM (with CLM, CAM-Chem)	UKRI Future Leaders Fellowship program	m.valmartin@sheffield.ac.uk
UiO	Norway	NorESM, CESM, CESM-WACCM, CAM, CLM(FATES)	INES2, NorESM4CMIP7, STEP CHANGE (ERC), WorldTrans (EU), LATICE, ACTIVATE (ERC), SnowLess	adagi@geo.uio.no , trude.storelvmo@geo.uio.no , yeliz.yilmaz@geo.uio.no
NORCE	Norway	NorESM, CISM	INES2, NorESM4CMIP7, FUTURA, RESCUE, iC3, NAVIGATE, MakingWaves, OceanNETs, PERMANOR, OCEAN ICE, SnowPI (EU)	mhen@norceresearch.no heig@norceresearch.no
MET	Norway	NorESM	INES2, NorESM4CMIP7, WorldTrans (EU), HyWay, ESA-SATACI, NAVIGATE, FUTURA, ENES-RISE	marianav@met.no , michaels@met.no

Institution	Country	Model/Component	Active Projects	Contact(s)
Stockholm University	Sweden	NorESM, CESM		sara.blichner@aces.su.se , frida.bender@misu.su.se , anna@misu.su.se
CMCC	Italy	CMCC-CESM, CLM CAM coupled with NEMO, Data Assimilation SPREADS, DART	FUTURA, C3S operational seasonal prediction, RESCUE, CONCERTO	silvio.gualdi@cmcc.it
DLR	Germany	CESM-MLe and ICON-MLe joint implementation group	BMFTR	veronika.eyring@dlr.de
AWI	Germany	CLM	SnowPI	Heidrun.Matthes@awi.de
TU Delft	The Netherlands	CESM2-CISM2, CESM-VR		M.Vizcaino@tudelft.nl
Utrecht University	The Netherlands	CESM (various versions, also HR and paleo), CISM		tim.vandenakker@geo.su.se
University of Leeds	UK	CESM (WACCM, WACCM-X, CAM-Chem)	NERC Meso-S2D, NERC DRIIVE, NERC MAGICA	d.marsh@leeds.ac.uk
Universidad de Vigo	Spain	CESM (WACCM, CAM-Chem)	SARTRE, ISSI Team 25-631	j.anel@uvigo.gal
Universidad Complutense de Madrid	Spain	CESM2 (WACCM, SCWACCM)	RETO-PV	nataliac@fis.ucm.es

Institution	Country	Model/Component	Active Projects	Contact(s)
CSIC	Spain	CESM2 (WACCM, SCWACCM)	SOCLIM (ERC-StG)	gabriel.chiodo@csic.es